

Third-Party Privacy Data Leak Analysis on Ontario Hospital Websites

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Abstract—This study investigates the privacy concerns associated with third-party data leaks on hospital websites in Ontario, Canada. The study employs both manual and automated analytics to investigate the privacy practices of 135 hospital websites in Ontario. This dual approach entails a thorough evaluation of websites while gathering and evaluating data-sharing policies. The findings show substantial variation in data-sharing procedures, with some hospital websites disclosing user data to third parties without explicit agreement, posing serious privacy issues. The study uncovers trends and abnormalities in data transfers, emphasizing the need for regulatory measures and enforcement to secure patient information. Furthermore, the findings highlight the critical need for strong privacy safeguards and regulatory frameworks in the healthcare industry. The study also makes practical recommendations for improving data privacy on hospital websites.

Index Terms—Data privacy, third-party data leaks, hospital websites, personally identifiable information (PII), privacy regulations.

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of digital technology into hospital services has markedly enhanced the accessibility and efficiency of healthcare delivery. As healthcare facilities increasingly rely on the internet to manage and disseminate patient information, the shift to digital platforms has brought forth significant privacy concerns, particularly regarding the unauthorized disclosure of personal data to third parties [1]. Hospitals, integral to the public sector, are leveraging digital technologies to improve operational effectiveness and patient engagement. However, this transition has introduced privacy risks associated with third-party services such as analytics tools, social networking plugins, and advertising networks. While these services offer enhanced functionality, they may compromise patient security and lead to unintended data sharing.

In Ontario, Canada, the Health Information Protection Act (PHIPA), alongside the Personal Information Protection and Electronic Documents Act (PIPEDA) and other privacy legislation, provides a regulatory framework for data protection.

PHIPA specifically governs the collection, use, and disclosure of personal health information by healthcare practitioners and organizations, while PIPEDA addresses broader privacy concerns, including those related to commercial activities.

PHIPA mandates strict regulations governing the collection, use, and dissemination of health information, requiring hospitals to obtain explicit patient consent prior to any disclosure. Similarly, PIPEDA underscores the importance of meaningful consent and transparency in data management practices. Despite these legal requirements, there have been documented instances of non-compliance and an inconsistent application of privacy protections on hospital websites. These issues are particularly concerning given the sensitive nature of health information and the potential ramifications of data breaches on patient privacy.

Globally, legislation such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) exacerbates privacy concerns for hospitals serving international patients. The GDPR imposes stringent consent requirements and transparency obligations on entities processing the personal data of EU residents [2]. For hospitals, this necessitates ensuring that all third-party services integrated into their digital platforms adhere to GDPR regulations, particularly those pertaining to data sharing and consent.

Recent studies have identified vulnerabilities related to third-party data sharing on hospital websites, revealing that many institutions fail to adequately protect patient information. For example, Huo et al. [3] found that many hospital websites share user data with third parties without adequate notification or consent, potentially breaching privacy regulations such as the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA). These deficiencies can result in unauthorized data exposure, an erosion of public trust, and the exposure of hospitals to legal liabilities.

Studies also illustrate the inconsistent adherence of hospital websites to privacy norms. Hamman and Osmar [4] argue that while some hospital websites have adopted robust privacy

measures, others, as reported by Uwizeyemungu and Poba-Nzaou [5], continue unauthorized data-sharing practices. This discrepancy highlights the urgent need for more stringent regulatory measures and enhanced enforcement to protect patient data.

The methodologies employed in existing research provide a range of insights but also reveal some limitations. Many studies rely on surveys and self-reported data, which may not fully capture the extent of unauthorized data-sharing practices. For instance, studies used dynamic taint analysis to track advanced tracking mechanisms and cookie data flow, highlighting significant privacy risks [1], [6]. Additionally, others conducted qualitative interviews with stakeholders to assess privacy measures [7], while others used content analysis to evaluate transparency in data handling [4].

This study examines the privacy practices of hospital websites with a focus on their compliance with relevant privacy legislation including PHIPA, PIPEDA, and the Privacy Act. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to explore third-party data leaks on Canadian hospital websites. The study investigates trends in third-party data sharing, assesses the effectiveness of privacy policies, and evaluates the adequacy of user consent mechanisms. By identifying gaps in privacy and transparency, this research underscores the necessity for enhanced privacy safeguards to protect patient information and uphold public trust in healthcare. As digital landscapes evolve, hospitals must continuously review and strengthen their privacy practices to meet legal requirements and ensure robust data security.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Types of Personal Data

This section investigates the different dimensions of data privacy within the Canadian legal framework, specifically analyzing the categories of Personal Health Information (PHI), Personally Identifiable Information (PII), and behavioral privacy.

1) *Personal Health Information (PHI)*: PHI encompasses any data related to an individual's health status, medical history, healthcare services received, or payment information for those services. Such information is safeguarded under Ontario's Personal Health Information Protection Act (PHIPA), alongside analogous regulations in other jurisdictions. PHI includes medical records, diagnostic reports, and any other information that could be utilized to identify an individual within the healthcare context.

2) *Personally Identifiable Information (PII)*: PII encompasses any data that can be utilized to identify an individual. This includes both explicit identifiers such as names, addresses, and Social Insurance Numbers (SIN), as well as more subtle information such as IP addresses and unique device identifiers. The protection of PII is regulated by federal legislation, specifically the Personal Information Protection and Electronic Documents Act (PIPEDA), along with corresponding provincial privacy laws [4].

3) *Behavioral Privacy*: Behavioral privacy pertains to the monitoring and analysis of individuals' online activities, such as browsing patterns, search history, and interactions with websites and online services. This data is often collected without explicit consent, which raises concerns about privacy violations, as extensive profiles of individuals may be developed without their knowledge or approval. In Canada, the collection and use of such data is subject to legislation requiring organizations to obtain consent and inform users of the nature and purpose of data collection [6].

Canadian privacy regulations mandate that organizations obtain informed consent before collecting, using, or disclosing personal information. This consent must be meaningful, ensuring that individuals fully understand what they are agreeing to, as well as the potential consequences of data sharing. The unauthorized disclosure of personal data can result in legal repercussions and may damage an organization's reputation [8].

B. Mechanisms of Web-Based Privacy Risks

This section examines the technical and privacy-related mechanisms by which hospital websites may expose user data to third-party entities. These mechanisms include the transmission of search terms and URLs, third-party event and page view tracking, and the aggregation of user behavior data, all of which pose significant privacy concerns.

1) *Tracking Technologies on Hospital Websites*: When users interact with hospital websites—particularly by entering search terms or accessing documents—their activity is often monitored using embedded third-party services such as Google Analytics. These services track user actions via JavaScript-based event listeners, page view tags, and cookies. For instance, a user searching for a term like “Kidney stone” on a hospital website may trigger a network request that transmits the search term and the corresponding URL (e.g., <https://providencecare.ca/?s=kidney+stone>) to a third-party analytics platform, as shown in Fig. 1. This process enables external services to capture the nature and context of user queries [9].

2) *Data Transmission and Storage*: Once captured, the data is sent to remote analytics servers where it is logged, stored, and analyzed. These transmissions often include interaction metadata such as tracking IDs (unique to the site), client or session identifiers, and document location URLs. This information allows third parties to associate user activity with specific hospital websites and link it to recurring sessions. Website administrators use these analytics dashboards to assess search behavior and user engagement; however, they also introduce privacy vulnerabilities due to the potential for sensitive health-related queries to be shared without adequate consent [4], [10].

3) *Profiling Through Device and Browser Metadata*: In addition to capturing explicit search input and page views, third-party tracking scripts collect passive metadata from the user's device and browser. This includes information such as language settings, screen resolution, operating system,

Fig. 1. Network Traffic Logs

and browser version—all extracted through the user agent string. These data points enable the creation of unique digital fingerprints that can identify users across sessions and potentially across different websites. Combined with session and client identifiers, such profiling raises concerns about de-anonymization and behavioral inference without the user’s awareness or approval [11].

4) *Privacy Implications:* The aggregation of search terms, URLs, and device metadata by third-party services has significant implications for patient privacy and data protection. While hospital websites may use these services for legitimate purposes such as site optimization, the data collected can reveal health conditions, interests, and patterns of behavior. Given that such information may fall under the scope of Personally Identifiable Information (PII) or even Personal Health Information (PHI), its unauthorized collection and sharing contravenes Canadian privacy regulations. These regulations, including the Personal Information Protection and Electronic Documents Act (PIPEDA) and Ontario’s Personal Health Information Protection Act (PHIPA), require organizations to obtain meaningful consent and to inform users of data collection practices in a transparent manner [4], [10].

Despite these legal requirements, the presence of embedded third-party services and opaque consent mechanisms poses a serious challenge to the enforcement of privacy standards on hospital websites. The potential for profiling, tracking, and unconsented data aggregation underscores the need for stronger privacy safeguards in the healthcare sector [9].

III. METHODOLOGY

In this study, we investigate the extent and nature of information transmitted to third-party services by analyzing hospital websites in Ontario, Canada, employing both manual and automated methods to capture and assess data-sharing practices.

The manual analysis involves a detailed examination of individual websites, where we actively interact with the site by performing searches and downloading documents. During this process, we monitor and document the specific data shared with third-party services [12]. Notably, third parties

often receive the URLs of the web pages visited by the user, revealing potentially sensitive information about the user’s activities, even when the user does not explicitly share search terms [3], [7].

The automated analysis used a previously developed Python script [13] to simulate user interactions with the hospital websites at scale. This allows us to systematically capture and analyze the data flow to third-party services across multiple websites efficiently and verify the results with the manual analysis [14]. By utilizing both analyses, we aim to identify consistent patterns and anomalies in the data-sharing practices of these hospital websites [15].

A. Manual Analysis

The manual component of our analysis involved the direct inspection of 135 hospital websites in Ontario to evaluate their data-sharing practices. This process was designed to simulate realistic user interactions by actively navigating each site, performing searches, accessing specific services, and downloading publicly available documents. During each session, we monitored outbound network requests to detect the transmission of user activity data to third-party domains, such as those belonging to analytics, advertising, and social media services.

Key aspects of the manual inspection included the identification of third-party trackers embedded within the site architecture, the presence of cookies, and the nature of any data transmitted during user interactions. Notably, URLs containing sensitive query parameters or document names were among the most frequently observed data types sent to third parties. These transmissions are concerning because they may reveal health-related search intent or behavior, even when the user has not explicitly shared personal information [7], [10], [16].

Our approach emphasized the documentation of specific patterns of third-party involvement. For instance, some websites consistently shared URLs with services like Google or Facebook, while others relied more narrowly on tools such as Cludo or Matomo Analytics. This helped highlight systemic inconsistencies in privacy practices across institutions. In particular, we found that some websites disclosed

user interactions to multiple external services, often without transparent consent mechanisms or visible privacy notices. These findings are elaborated in later sections, which provide detailed breakdowns of third-party request frequency and service involvement.

B. Automatic Analysis

The automated script is designed to test the search bars of various web pages, focusing on whether the search terms entered by users are collected by third parties, such as advertisers and analytics providers. This script leverages web scraping techniques to target specific HTML elements and attributes, with additional logic to accommodate nested structures that may indicate search functions.

The script operates by reading a list of URLs from a UTF-8 encoded text file, provided as an argument upon execution. Each URL is required to include the full scheme (“https://” or “http://”) to ensure accurate parsing. Once initiated, the script prompts the user to enter a search term, which is then utilized across the listed web pages. As the script processes each page, it logs information to the command line, generates an HTML report, and captures a screenshot of the tested page. It is crucial to note that if a generated HTML report does not display the search term at the top, manual verification is recommended to confirm the absence of a search bar.

Key functions within the script include **“handle request event()”**, which monitors network requests generated during the search process. This function filters requests for inclusion in the HTML report based on specific criteria: the request contains the search term, is sent to a different address than the current page, or matches a pattern indicative of third-party analytics tools. Another vital function is **“is search related()”**, which determines whether a given HTML element is associated with search functions based on its attributes. This function is critical for identifying input fields and buttons utilized in searches.

The script also addresses potential challenges such as click interception, where elements may obstruct the intended search action. In such cases, the script employs JavaScript to remove the obstructing element, ensuring that the search can proceed without interruption. Our automated script provides a systematic approach to evaluating potential privacy risks associated with search functions on web pages, offering valuable insights into the collection and potential sharing of search terms and other data by third parties.

IV. RESULTS

In this section, we present findings from the analysis of 135 hospital websites listed by the Ontario Hospital Association (OHA) [17], focusing on privacy risks related to third-party tracking, data sharing, and the presence of privacy policies. Data were collected using both manual inspection and automated testing scripts.

A. Third-Party Requests and Tracking Behavior

Our analysis identified a total of 823 third-party requests across the hospital websites, with Google accounting for 545

of those requests, making it the dominant recipient of user interaction data. Figure 2 represents the distribution of these third-party requests across services such as Google, Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, Matomo Analytics, Cludo, and Kickfire Analytics [18].

A total of 86 distinct third parties were the recipients of requests that leaked private data. The type of data being leaked to third parties is also of concern, as it often includes data taken from the URLs of users’ searches. Figure 1 shows an example of network traffic for a search for the term ‘Kidney stone.’ The search is entered into the Providence Care website and included in the URL. In some cases, the search terms can be passed on to third parties as well, which could mean that private data entered into a hospital page by the user could be shared with a third party without the user’s knowledge.

These requests were generated either directly by user interactions or passively through embedded scripts and page loads. For example, accessing a homepage like “https://example.com/” triggered additional calls to resources such as “https://images.example.com/logo.png” or to analytics services—even without explicit user input. This distinction between user-initiated and automatically triggered requests reveals potential opacity in data transmission processes.

It is important to note that these numbers represent averages and that behaviors varied across individual websites. Some sites showed limited third-party involvement, while others initiated multiple analytics and tracking requests on each visit.

The analysis of data sharing practices revealed significant variability in how user data is handled during website interactions. In certain instances, data was shared with third parties without the explicit consent of users, raising critical concerns about privacy and data protection [6].

B. Privacy Policies

The visibility and accessibility of privacy policies, which serve as key indicators of an organization’s commitment to data privacy, also varied significantly across the studied websites. There were instances where privacy policies were not prominently displayed, potentially leading to user unawareness regarding the organization’s data practices [19]. In contrast, other websites featured prominently displayed privacy policies, ensuring that users were well-informed about the organization’s data handling practices [14].

Table I reveals that the majority of the websites that we examined have a privacy policy, however, less than ten percent of them properly allow the user to consent to that policy. Therefore, users are not able to properly consent to the way their data is processed and shared.

TABLE I
PERCENTAGE OF PRESENCE OF PRIVACY POLICIES AND CONSENT ON HOSPITAL WEBSITES

	Yes	No
Presence of Privacy Policies	80%	20%
Presence of Consent Request	9.6%	90.4%

Fig. 2. Third Party Request

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study investigates privacy risks associated with third-party data collection on 135 hospital websites in Ontario, Canada. By employing both manual inspection and automated testing tools, we systematically analyzed how search terms, browsing activity, and other interaction data are transmitted to external analytics and advertising platforms—often without the user’s knowledge or consent.

Our findings reveal widespread integration of third-party services, most notably Google Analytics, with 823 third-party requests recorded during our analysis, over 500 of which were directed to Google. While 80% of websites included some form of privacy policy, fewer than 10% employed explicit consent mechanisms for data collection. This gap in privacy safeguards raises important questions about compliance with Canadian regulations such as PIPEDA and PHIPA.

Key Contributions. This research makes several important contributions to the field of digital health privacy: (1) It introduces a dual-method approach combining manual and automated techniques to uncover hidden third-party data sharing practices. (2) It specifically investigates the behavior of hospital website search functions—an underexplored aspect in prior literature. (3) It quantifies the visibility of privacy policies and the presence of consent requests, highlighting areas of non-compliance. (4) It provides an actionable framework for identifying privacy risks in the healthcare web ecosystem.

Our analysis underscores the complexity and multifaceted nature of website privacy risk assessment, emphasizing the need for rigorous and nuanced methodologies to ensure ethical data practices [16].

Recommendations. Based on our research findings, we recommend that hospitals consider adopting privacy-friendly alternatives to Google Analytics, such as Matomo or Piwik

PRO, for onsite analytic services. These platforms offer significant advantages in terms of data privacy and security. Unlike Google Analytics, which involves data transfer to third-party servers, Matomo and Piwik PRO ensure that website visitor data remains within the hospital’s control. This approach aligns with best practices in data protection by eliminating the risk of unauthorized data sharing and providing enhanced oversight over the collected information. By implementing these alternatives, hospitals can maintain compliance with privacy regulations and better protect sensitive visitor information, ultimately fostering greater trust and transparency with patients and stakeholders.

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